

TEACHING SPEAKING BY SPEECH ACTIVITIES ARTICLE**Student: Hamrayeva Zamira****Tashkent region Chirchik State Pedagogical University****Faculty of Tourism Foreign languages and literature,****hamrayeva17@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8005656>**

Abstract The main objective of learning English is using English as a means of communication. One of the ways for the teachers to make the students use English as a means of communications using appropriate techniques which match with the learners' characteristics in teaching speaking. Unfortunately, the fact shows that many teachers still do not know the appropriate techniques to teach speaking for the students. They frequently teach speaking using translation and memorizing techniques, whereas, those techniques are not appropriate with the characteristics of young learners. In this case, the teachers have to know the applicable techniques for teaching speaking to the students to achieve the main objective of teaching English. Thus, this article will explain some of communicative activities which can be used by the teachers in teaching speaking.

Keywords: phenomenology; effects; technology; teaching speaking; focus group discussion

INTRODUCTION

speaking can be defined as the process of sharing information between speaker and listener in any circumstances. It becomes very indispensable since it is used to convey ideas or arguments particularly in the classroom setting. Speaking is one of language skills learned by the students in a foreign language. It involves a process of building and sharing meaning through the use of language orally. By learning speaking, the students will know the way to express language communicatively. The students will learn how to express utterances meaningfully. Besides that, it also leads them to make interaction in the society by using the language. Because of that, speaking is one of important skill that should be mastered by the students in learning foreign language. As a matter of fact, the use of English for speaking is not simple for the students, because they have to master several important elements, such as pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, fluency and comprehension. These elements are very important in the communication because if they do not master all the elements of speaking, the communication will not run very smoothly. In addition, speaking in a new language is believed to be harder than reading, writing, or listening for two reasons. First, unlike reading or writing, speaking happens in real time: usually the person you are talking to is waiting for you to speak right then. Second, when someone speaks, he/she can not edit and revise what he/she wishes to say, as he/she can if he/she is writing.

LITERATURE REVIEW

There is a mushrooming body of research about how speaking is taught to students especially using the English language. This is because of the knowledge that teachers resourceful as they are resorting to different strategies, techniques and approaches in developing and shaping the speaking skill of students. They use various ways and implement different methodologies in developing student's communicative competence. They design courses to help students find English learning more enjoyable for them to develop a better attitude (Noom-ura, 2008).

Various researches have been conducted to find out which approaches and strategies are the best and more effective in developing communicative competence. Koşar (2019) determined the significant difference in speaking performances of students being taught by native and non-native English speakers. Some even recommended knowledge and practice in developing speaking skills after a research study. Murad and Smadi (2009) recommended that teachers may adopt task-based language teaching principles and procedures in their classroom practices within and pre-service training programs to develop teachers' ability to use task-based language teaching when designing and executing lesson plans. Yüzlü and Derin (2020) examined the impact of the use of L1 on the EFL learners' L2 speaking skills as well as their perceptions of L1 use in fostering oral production in L2. Some conducted research on effectivity of a strategy used in developing communicative competence. Qing (2011) stated that role play is a very valuable method to help learners to interact and provide them an opportunity to practice in the target language context. It further suggested the application of role plays to increase student's intercultural awareness and to help them develop overall communicative competence. More so, Aliakbari and Jamalvandi (2010) stated that role play is a praised technique in task-based language teaching which has a positive effect on students' speaking skills. Besides, utilizing technology in teaching methods is a fundamental practice in teaching EFL, where it is available and accessible. Suggestions to incorporate the use of technology in teaching speaking have been stated. The use of CMC (computer-mediated communication) in teaching pronunciation and conversation is put forward to improve students' oral skills (Hong, 2006). With the technology used in teaching language skills, McDougald (2009) also revealed that ICT is definitely a complement to conventional teaching, especially when developing reading, writing and listening skills in English. The use of technology in teaching speaking is one of the changes in how languages are taught in school which focuses on the use of language communication rather than just passing the examination (Thao, 2003).

2. Method

2.1 Sample / Participants

There were three sets of participants involved in this study. Each set is composed of seven students from sophomore, junior and senior language classes of the Bachelor of Secondary Education program of the University of Southern Mindanao Kidapawan City Campus, Philippines. Stratified random sampling was conducted to identify the participants from each language class section. Each of the students' names was written on a small piece of paper and was picked and chosen as participants. This gives all students an equal chance to be the participants of the study thus avoiding biases in the selection process. From each section, seven names were picked. From the three sections of the language class, three sets of Focus Group Discussion (FGD) participants were formed with seven participants per set with a total of 21 students. These participants have already enrolled and passed the speaking courses. They were taught by different instructors of the same level in terms of educational attainment and status of permanency. Participants were chosen regardless of sex and gender. They were of the same age ranging from 17-19 years old. They are all majoring in English in their BSE program.

2.2 Instrument / Material

To extract data, this research study used a question guide formulated from the research questions. There were two research questions with at least five probing questions each with which were subjected to experts' evaluation and validation. The question guide was used to interview the participants during the focus group discussion from which the data were extracted.

2.3 Data Collection and Analysis

This study was first proposed and presented to the University

research department for suggestions and approval. After which was the permission of the campus university chancellor for the conduct of the study. Secondly, after the approval was given, the researcher met the three sections of the language class. Students were explained the research content, problem, procedure, outcome and everything about the research project. The researcher built rapport towards the students at this phase to develop friendship and ease which helped extract genuine answers from the questions during the conduct of the FGD. Then, the researcher asked permission of the students to become the participants of the study.

3. Results and Discussion Table 1. The technology used in teaching speaking Themes Frequency of response Core ideas video conferencing general "She talks to us on videos using skype." (FGD2CS2) email correspondence general "First, she asked us to have an official and professional email account. She tells [told] us to have one." FGD1S7 social media conversation general She employed authentic tasks like using social media for conversation..." FGD2S1 emceeing and on-stage speaking performances typical "... she requested most of us as masters of ceremonies in university programs and events throughout the semester." FGD3S6 Legend: General 50% up Typical 25% - 40% Variant 20% down Table 1 shows the technology used by instructors in teaching speaking. The three groups of Focus Group Discussion (FGD) detailed that students were taught by language instructors to speak in English with the use of technology in carrying out communicative tasks. It was found that instructors made use of the available technology in employing task-based activities. Generally, instructors did video conferencing, email correspondence and social media conversation. Emceeing and on-stage speaking performances on the other hand are done typically. Video conferencing was done as participants detailed. They said: "We talk[ed] in the group at night using Skype video especially during our home reading activity." FGD1S3 "When our instructor miss[ed] the class, she conducted makeup classes through video conference on messenger and she starts[ed] to lecture and instructs. . ." FGD2S4 Video conferencing on Skype and messenger as what the participants stated above was done by the instructor to cope with the missed classes and as a supplemental activity to give way for the lecture

CONCLUSION

The results of the study revealed that the technologies of today have become an effective platform in teaching speaking. It is an additional input of instructors apart from lecturing. Instructors do not employ traditional approaches nor use outmoded modes of teaching speaking like chalk and board lecture in tasking the students to learn to speak, instead, they make use of the technologies of today as their medium. After laying down the results of this study, it can be concluded that instructors make use of technological tools in carrying out tasks for students learning to speak in English. Technology tools such as video conferencing, email correspondence and social media conversation were found to have been used in general. These technological tools where tasks are channelled build rapport, increase fluency and accuracy, ease anxiety and apprehension and build confidence amongst students who learn to speak in English. These tools help students become skillful and competent in speaking.

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